

COMPANY RESILIENCE IN THE EUROPEAN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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WHICH FIRM-LEVEL CHARACTERISTICS FACILITATE THE RESILIENCE OF COMPANIES COMPETING IN THE EUROPEAN TOURISM INDUSTRY?

INTRODUCTION

Crises carry economic and social costs and, thus, understanding how to improve company resilience is crucial to reduce such costs and prepare firms to survive future disruptions (Bertschek, Polder and Schulte, 2019). This is a very relevant industry for the European economy, representing 10.3% of its GDP (European Parliament, 2022). The tourism industry is also of particular interest given that it was severely harmed during previous outbreaks of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (Zeng, Carter and de Lacy, 2005; Chen, Jang and Kim, 2007). Interestingly, recent research shows that not all companies competing in the tourism sector have struggled with this pandemic. Some of them actually thrived, like Domino's Pizza, Haidilao International, and Xi'an Tourism (Kaczmarek et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

To provide broader insight into the topic of firm resilience and develop a clear framework of the main findings concerning the resilience of companies operating in the tourism industry, a systematic literature review was conducted following the approach proposed by Denyer and Tranfield (2009), in consideration of the recommendations proposed by Rojon, Okupe and McDowall (2021).

RESULTS

This literature review identifies a multidimensional nature of the concept of company resilience as a set of attributes that firms can improve to become more resilient to external shock. The evolution of the existing literature on this subject points out a dynamic nature of resilience (Gittell et al., 2006; Vogus and Sutcliffe, 2007; Brown et al., 2017) consistent with the dynamic capabilities view, instead of a more static perspective expressed in the earlier studies. This suggests that companies can adopt behaviors and build competencies that foster resilience (Lengnick-Hall, Beck and Lengnick-Hall, 2011), instead of being condemned by the presence or absence of such attribute. This dynamic view also implies that resilience is not an "one size fits all" concept.

REFERENCES

Bertschek, I., Polder, M. and Schulte, P. (2019) 'ICT and resilience in times of crisis: evidence from cross-country micro moments data', *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 28(8), pp. 759–774. Brown, N.A. et al. (2017) 'Exploring disaster resilience within the hotel sector: A systematic review of literature', *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 22, pp. 362–370. Chen, M.-H., Jang, S.S. and Kim, W.G. (2007) 'The impact of the SARS outbreak on Taiwanese hotel stock performance: An event-study approach', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 26(1), pp. 200–212. Denyer, D. and Tranfield, D. (2009) 'Producing a Systematic Review', in *The SAGE Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*. Sage Publications Ltd., pp. 671–689. European Parliament (2022) *Tourism | Fact Sheets on the European Union | European Parliament*. Available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/126/tourism>; Gittell, J.H. et al. (2006) 'Relationships, Layoffs, and Organizational Resilience', *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 42(3), pp. 300–329. Kaczmarek, T. et al. (2021) 'How to survive a pandemic: The corporate resiliency of travel and leisure companies to the COVID-19 outbreak', *Tourism Management*, 84, p. 104281. Lengnick-Hall, C.A., Beck, T.E. and Lengnick-Hall, M.L. (2011) 'Developing a capacity for organizational resilience through strategic human resource management', *Human Resource Management Review*, 21(3), pp. 243–255. Rojon, C., Okupe, A. and McDowall, A. (2021) 'Utilization and development of systematic reviews in management research: What do we know and where do we go from here?', *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 23(2), pp. 191–223. Vogus, T.J. and Sutcliffe, K.M. (2007) 'Organizational resilience: Towards a theory and research agenda', in *2007 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*. IEEE, pp. 3418–3422. Zeng, B., Carter, R.W. and de Lacy, T. (2005) 'Short-term Perturbations and Tourism Effects: The Case of SARS in China', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 8(4), pp. 306–322.

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